

Welcome to the April newsletter, lots of news to share and events and resources for you. Enjoy!

In this issue...

- [Transcripts from Glasgow joint LNL & IL discussions](#)
- [Previous LNL workshops - now resources for you](#)
- [Upcoming LNL workshops](#)
- [UKRN webinars](#)
- [LNL presentations during Open Research Weeks](#)
- [Reading recommendation](#)
- [LEGO® Metadata for Reproducibility game](#)
- [All this could be yours](#)

University of Strathclyde IL Madeleine Grealy and LNL Christine Dufes in conversation in Glasgow

Transcripts from Glasgow joint LNL & IL discussions

During this joint meeting we ran discussion sessions on how can UKRN can best support ILs and LNLs in their role, career progression, and priorities for UKRN. It was classic flipchart and marker pen stuff with lots of enthusiastic debate. We've transcribed all the notes made that day and whilst the UKRN central team need to reflect upon these we also want to share them with you - [here](#).

Seeing what others have said in response to these topics may help you reflect upon your own role, the relationship with your local network and institution, or avenues you wish to explore. As always, if you have any comments please get in touch.

Previous LNL workshops - now resources for you

Workshop 1: Setting up a student consortium for undergraduate final year projects

A recording of the presentation by Kait Clark (LNL University of the West of England - UWE) is now [available](#). If anyone would like to be included in a future student consortium please contact Kait.

Workshop 2: Building the LNL – Open Research Enabler relationship

This workshop brought together LNLs and open research enablers, including ORCAs (Open Research Coordinators & Administrators based at institutes involved in the UKRN Open Research Programme) to learn more about communications within their institute so they can be more effective in their respective roles.

A recording of the presentations is [here](#). Steve Boneham provided some example [templates](#) of event flyers and emails. To be clear, not all LNLs may wish to undertake all these activities, they are intended as a resource for inspiration.

Talks – offer to give an open research presentation in a different department, use senior management contacts e.g. IL as the way in.

Create challenging conversations – engage those who think open research has nothing to do with them.

Advertising – piggyback onto existing networks and events. Use discipline specific messaging.

Departmental meetings – get items on the agenda and attend them, cross promote things within them, they're well attended.

Strategic people – find people who have strategic input, search institutional open research webpages/documents to identify authors or people consulted. Once you've made links with them sprinkle their names into emails and adverts to give you a little bit more clout.

Library staff - often the first point of call for people interested in open research, so linking in with them is key. They know where there are pockets of activity/inactivity around open research across an institution.

Practicalities – create a spreadsheet listing all contacts made across the university and who should follow up with them (the ORCA, LNL or IL), what actions there are.

Upcoming LNL workshops

Workshop 4: Understanding the workings of an institution

This will be presented by Etienne Roesch, former LNL now IL at University of Reading.

To deploy change at scale LNLs need institutional support. Etienne will share his experience of the practical steps needed to reach the right people in the right way, and how he used this understanding to develop policies within his institution.

2 May 13:00– 14:00 Register [here](#)

Workshop 5: Mindset awareness

This will be presented by Nikki Osborne, Director of [Responsible Research in Practice](#). An awareness of how mindset can impact research culture can help discussions on how to support change. The workshop will enable LNLs to work together on activities to understand more about fixed and growth mindsets, and to reflect on how these mindsets affect themselves and others

13 June 13:00pm – 14:00pm Register [here](#)

December workshop: Replication games – all day event

It's a long way off but we're so excited we wanted to share the details with you. This will be an all-day event run by Abel Brodeur from the [Institute for Replication](#). Consider it an early Christmas present from us to you. More details to follow

5 December 9:30 – 17:30 Register [here](#)

Would **YOU like to run a workshop?**

We still have a few slots left. Get in touch contact@ukrn.org

UKRN webinars

Reproducibility, transparency, positionality?

Perspectives
from different
research fields

Online Workshop
18th April 2024

Reproducibility, transparency, positionality? Perspectives from different research fields

April 18 13:00 - 15:00

In this webinar, speakers from arts practice, astronomy, psychology, and qualitative social sciences outline their perspectives on these questions, with the aim of highlighting both diversity and perhaps surprising commonalities. The webinar marks the release of a new UKRN working paper, based on a recent facilitated dialogue between arts practice and psychology researchers, sponsored by the British Psychological Society, the Practice Research Advisory Group, and UKRN. Register [here](#)

Introduction to power analysis via simulation in R

**Insect Welfare
Research Society**

Online workshop
16th May 2024

Introduction to power analysis via simulation in R

May 16 13:00 - 15:00

The goal of this webinar is to provide a functional introduction to performing power analyses via simulation. Power analyses are vital tools that can provide an estimate of sample sizes required for a given experiment. Participants will be guided through the code needed to run their own simulations and are encouraged to bring their own experiment plans for live, interactive

analysis. Register [here](#).

The March 2024 UKRN webinar '**Indicators for Open Research: Pilot Projects**' was very well attended and has been popular on Youtube. You can watch it [here](#).

Other events

[TIER 2 Reproducibility Café - Reproducibility Management Plans](#)

April 24 9:00 - 11:00 UK time

Reproducibility Café focused on developing a prototype plan for managing reproducibility activities in research projects. More info [here](#) Register [here](#)

[Open Research Conference Manchester Museum](#)

Wednesday April 24 in-person event

The University of Manchester is hosting its first ever Open Research Conference. More info [here](#). Register [here](#).

[Teaching study design and analysis: A workshop based on UK-wide, cross-disciplinary survey of teaching practices for life sciences](#)

University of Manchester, June 12

A 1-day workshop to foster communication among disciplines and improve teaching in study design and analysis, with an eye to support science reform by improving research transparency and reproducibility. More info and workshop itinerary [here](#).

[Sign up](#) to indicate interest registration link will follow.

LNL presentations during Open Research Weeks

It's been great to see our LNLs giving presentations on aspects of open research close to their hearts as part of university events this spring. The University of Liverpool hosted several talks and a panel discussion including: Alexis Makin (University of Liverpool) 'How to advance your career by publishing fewer papers'

Krzysztof Cipora (Loughborough University) 'What if you can't share your data: synthetic datasets'

Andrew Jones (Liverpool John Moore's University) 'How to advance science by 'publishing' everything you do'

Osama Mahmoud (recently moved to IL University of Essex) 'Dynamic Reporting' and Michel Belyk (Edge Hill University).

Read more [here](#). The recording is [here](#).

Northumbria University hosted a similar event with:

David Smailes (Northumbria University) 'Open Research Practices and the Peer Review Problem'

Grant Abt (University of Hull) 'Registered Reports in the Journal of Sports Sciences'

Will Cawthorn (University of Edinburgh) 'Open Scholarship policies and practices across European Universities'

The recording is [here](#).

Reading recommendation

Reproducible, scalable, & shareable
ENVIRONMENTAL DATA SCIENCE

Illustration by Scriberia as part of The Turing Way book dash in November 2021. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5706310>

The [Environmental Data Science book \(EDS book\)](#) is a living, open and community-driven online resource to showcase and support the publication of data, research and open-source tools for collaborative, reproducible and transparent Environmental Data Science. Alejandro Coca Castro, one of the new LNLs at the Alan Turing Institute, was recently awarded a Dorothy Bishop Prize for his work on this initiative. Read about all 3 prize winners [here](#)

LEGO® Metadata for Reproducibility game

Here at UKRN we love LEGO and this is a great LEGO activity from the University of Glasgow for you to do with your local network members. An interactive game for 4 - 24 players, it includes planning for metadata and draws

parallels between recording and communicating the research process. Discussion on how metadata is captured, recorded and disseminated also provides opportunities to signpost resources. If you do run this activity, please send us photos of the event. More info and downloads [here](#).

All this could be yours

Become a guest editor! Would you like to contribute an article or become a guest editor? Just imagine, a whole issue dedicated to an area of open research close to your heart. Get in touch and we'll support you in making it a reality contact@ukrn.org